

Natural enemies of the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* in the Philippines

A. T. Barrion, J. P. Bandong, M. D. Lumaban, P. C. Pantua, R. A. Apostol, and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Only a braconid *Apanteles angustibasis* Gahan and a chalcid *Brachymeria excarinata* Gahan have been reported to parasitize the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* in the Philippines.

From 1976 to 1978 we expanded the list of parasites of the rice leaf folder by including data on its natural enemies at its four life stages, from four Philippine provinces representing irrigated (Laguna),rainfed wetland (Iloilo and Pangasinan),and dryland (Batangas) rice improvements(see table). We exposed rice plants laden with eggs in the field but recovered no egg parasites. We held field – collected larvae and pupae and recorded seven new parasites. Through field observation and follow-up laboratory studies we determined seven new predators of the larval or adult stages.

List of parasites and predators of the rice leaf folder, Philippines, 1976-78.			
Parasite	Life stage of leaf folder	Predator	Life stage of leaf folder
Hymenoptera		Coleoptera (det. A.T. Barrion)	
Braconidae (det. A.T. Barrion)		Carabidae	
<i>Apanteles angustibasis</i> Gahan	Larva	<i>Desera geniculata</i> (Klug)	Larva
<i>Cardiochiles philippinensis</i> Ashmead ^{a/}	Larva	<i>Chlaenius</i> sp. ^{a/}	Larva
<i>Macrocentrus philippinensis</i> Ashmead ^{a/}	Larva	Hymenoptera (det. A.T. Barrion)	
Ichneumonidae (det. G. Chandra)		Formicidae	
<i>Temelucha stangli</i> (Ashmead) ^{a/}	Larva	<i>Odontomachus</i> sp. ^{a/}	Larva
<i>Trichomma cnaphalocrosis</i> Uchida ^{a/}	Larva-pupa	<i>Solenopsis geminata</i> var.	Larva
<i>Xanthopimpla flavolineata</i> Cameron ^{a/}	Larva	<i>rufa</i> (Jerdon),	
Chalcididae (det. A.T. Barrion)		Araneida	
<i>Brachymeria excarinata</i> Gahan	Larva-pupa	Oxyopidae	
Bethylidae (det. A.T. Barrion)		<i>Oxyopes javanus</i> Thorell ^{a/}	Larva & adult
<i>Goniozus</i> nr. <i>Indicus</i> Muesebeck ^{a/}	Larva	Argiopidae	
Diptera		<i>Argiope amulus</i> ^{a/}	Adult
Tachinidae (det. H. Shima)		<i>Nephila maculata</i> ^{a/}	Adult
<i>Argyrophylax nigrotibialis</i> (Baranov) ^{a/}	Larva		
New Philippine record.			